

ANALYSIS OF THE DYADIC RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN LEADER AND SUPPORTERS IN TEAM WORK AT AN AUTOMOTIVE COMPANY

Author(s)*: Dan MIRICESCU ¹, Alice-Maria DEACONU ²

Position: Prof., PhD¹, Eng.²

University: "Lucian Blaga" University of Sibiu¹, Thyssenkrupp Bilstein SA Sibiu²

Address: Sibiu, Victoriei Blvd., No. 10, Romania

Email: dan.miricescu@ulbsibiu.ro¹, alicedeaconu@yahoo.com²

Webpage: <http://www.ulbsibiu.ro/>

Abstract

Purpose – *The paper aims to study and analyze the existing relationships between leaders and supporters within an automotive company from Sibiu, in order to emphasize the importance that can be developed between the two components of the dyad, from the perspective of the work climate and the performance.*

Methodology/approach – *The study is based on two questionnaires distributed to both team leaders and employees (team members) within the company, with most similar questions, precisely to see the opinions of the two components of the dyad. The research is a quantitative type, trying to capture the typology of existing relationships in a company with a productive profile.*

Findings – *At the level of the studied company, communication is efficient and satisfactory, from the perspective of correlating the level of expectations with that of the perceived reality, both for employees and for leaders. Communication is carried out in a relaxed, friendly manner, characterized by availability for collaboration, consultation, offering useful information and support.*

Research limitations/implications – *The paper focuses only on one company, with a clear field of activity. In order to extend the conclusions to a wider level, it is necessary to extend the study to a larger number of companies and even to a variation of their field of activity.*

Practical implications – *Communicating the results of the analysis to the company's management clarified, to a large extent, the image related to the work climate within the organization and highlighted the means to regulate relationships, so that they evolve towards higher standards.*

Originality/value – *The contribution brought by this study, carried out at the request of those in the company, is related to the identification of a real situation and the identification in an objective way of the typology of the dyadic relationship between leaders and supporters within a company focused on the production side, where, usually, relationships are more tense and the pressure of short deadlines in honoring orders can leave its mark on the quality of these relationships.*

Key words: *leadership, relationship, supporters.*

Introduction

We are living in a stage where the paradigm in which the business environment is designed is increasingly complex, a stage being characterized by much turbulence and uncertainties, which leave a substantial mark on the elements of performance and sustainability. One certainty in this complex situation is the way in which leadership leaves its mark on relationships within organizations, the way in which an organizational culture based on trust is generated, which determines organizational sustainability even in difficult times. From this point of view, leadership is that binder that can offer relevant solutions by creating a connection between the management area and the work teams, transferring trust and a clear vision regarding the organizational evolution and opening communication channels and levers of influence to come from work teams, supporters, employees. Moreover, in an organization focused on production, within an industry that has major challenges regarding business market developments, leadership can be the one that offers stable and pertinent solutions regarding the construction of a people-centered culture that leads to performance.

In recent years, awareness of this issue has increased worldwide. The importance of studying and understanding the phenomenon called "leadership" is recognized. Discovering the "secret" that is the basis of effective leadership would contribute substantially to the development of organizations' ability to classify and help to evolve managers and leaders. In order to better understand the current trends regarding the concept of leadership, (Zohar, I., 2016)

Many leadership researchers have focused more on leaders and paid less attention to supporters (employees). Lately, more and more researchers have put, and emphasize, the dyadic approach, a concept that is based on the relationships (relationship systems) between the leader and the supporter in some work subunit. The dyadic approach to leadership tries to explain why leader behavior varies from one follower to another. The dyadic approach also shows the different behaviors of the supporters towards the leader. For example, if the supporters' opinion about the leader is tested, it is possible to see two categories of dyadic relations: one group characterizes the relations with the leader as positive and another group as negative (Țuțurea, Miricescu, Moraru, Grecu, 2010).

The research on dyadic leadership differs from other theories of leadership that address generalized leader behaviors and traits to all followers. For instance, dyadic relationships, assumes that leaders differentiate among subordinates in the establishment of these relationships, and describes a role-making process that leads to the development of the relationships. The dyadic approach is also concerned with the outcomes of these relationships for individuals and the organization. (Brower, H. H., Schoorman, F. D., and Tan, H. H., 2000)

General elements regarding the realization of the study

The research whose analysis is presented was carried out on the basis of a questionnaire within a company whose main activity is the production of auto components in the industrial area of the municipality of Sibiu. The main objective of the research is to highlight the existing relationships between employees (supporters) and leaders within work teams, trying to highlight the fact that the existing dyadic relationship between the two components can be influenced by each component of the dyad. Precisely for this reason, two types of questionnaires were administered, with many similar questions, one with the target group of team members within the company (the so-called supporters, from the point of view of leadership theory), and the other targeting the team leaders within the company. For this reason, there is also an imbalance between the numbers of respondents from the two types of questionnaires, the team leaders being a much smaller group than the company's employees. According with these specifications, the application of the questionnaire had in mind a representative sample, the target population being the employees and leaders of the automotive company. The first questionnaire targets the company's employees, and the research was carried out on a sample of 147 employees from different departments. The second questionnaire targets leaders within the company, and the research was carried out on a sample of 21 leaders of different departments. The departments included in the research were: the production department, the quality department, the purchasing department, the accounting department, the human resources department.

In accordance with the main objective of the research, several secondary objectives were developed, each with several working hypotheses to be verified as part of the analysis of the questionnaire results. Thus, the following secondary objectives and the following working hypotheses were established:

Objective 1: Measuring the level of relationship between leaders and supporters within the automotive company

Hypothesis 1: Seniority in the workplace may lead to more effective networking due to more in-depth knowledge of internal procedures, manufacturing processes, and personnel.

Hypothesis 2: In a company where the employee has the freedom to plan, schedule, organize and control his own work, it can lead to more effective communication with leaders because the employee is trusted to make decisions.

Hypothesis 3: The involvement of employees in decision-making and the improvement of processes within the company can ensure a more effective relationship between leaders and supporters by reaching the need to confirm their skills.

Objective 2: Measuring the degree of satisfaction, involvement and motivation of the staff in the actions aimed at increasing the performance of relations with their leaders.

Hypothesis 1: Employee satisfaction is found in the level of involvement and motivation through effective actions of the company.

Hypothesis 2: The level of motivation of employees is found in the quality of relationships.

Objective 3: Identifying the degree of satisfaction of the relationship within the company both from the point of view of the employees and the leaders.

Hypothesis: Within a successful company, the level of satisfaction of relations between leaders and supporters must be perceived equally by both parties involved, avoiding situations where the relationship is considered optimal only from the perspective of employees or leaders.

The process of analysis and interpretation of the data obtained following the application of the questionnaires will be done taking into account the research objectives and hypotheses.

The level of relationship between leaders and supporters within the automotive company

Hypothesis 1: Seniority in the workplace may lead to more effective networking due to more in-depth knowledge of internal procedures, manufacturing processes, and personnel.

Fig. 1: How long have you worked for this company? (Supporters – left, Leaders – right)

Analyzing the answers received following the question, "How long have you worked in this company?", from the company's employees it can be observed a majority percentage for a seniority between 3 to 7 years (34.4%), respectively over 7 years (34.4%). Regarding the response of the leaders, it can be observed that the majority response falls within the same seniority within the company, 3 to 7 years (35.3%), respectively over 7 years (29.4%). Considering the previously mentioned hypothesis, through the seniority of the employees and leaders, it can be deduced that within the company analyzed, the activity is carried out with employees and leaders who appreciate the values and professional relations within the company. Seniority on the job leads to more effective networking due to more in-depth knowledge of internal procedures, manufacturing processes and personnel.

Hypothesis 2: In a company where the employee has the freedom to plan, schedule, organize and control his own work, it can lead to more effective communication with leaders because the employee is trusted to make decisions.

Fig. 2: Do you have the freedom to plan, schedule, organize and control your own work? (Supporters – left); Do you give employees freedom to plan, schedule, organize and control their own work? (Leaders – right)

59.4% of company employees appreciate that they have the freedom to plan, schedule, organize and control their own work, and 28.1% answered that they are sometimes allowed to do this. 81.8% of company leaders appreciate that they encourage employees to plan, schedule, organize and control their own work.

From the answers given, we can highlight that within the company employees are encouraged to take responsibility for the activities they carry out. Through the freedom to organize and plan their own way of working, trust is given to employees, this being a very good supporter of the relationship between them and the leaders. By encouraging employees to control their own work, leaders can achieve higher performance by empowering employees. Employees know their tasks much better, so communication between them can be free of employees' fear of failing or giving wrong information.

Fig. 3: Are the objectives to be met established with your participation or are they simply passed on to you by the leader? (Supporters – left); Are the objectives to be met set with employee participation or are they simply passed on? (Leaders – right)

In terms of setting the objectives to be met, both employees (37.5% set with employees and 31.3% sometimes set with employees) and leaders (63.6% set with employees and 27.3% sometimes are established with employees) of the company believes that to a high extent they are established together with the team. A small discrepancy can be observed between the considerations of employees and leaders, the latter giving a much higher percentage to the transmission of objectives.

Fig. 4: Do you know the results expected by the leader from you? (Supporters – left); Are the results expected by you transmitted to the employees? (Leaders – right)

In order for the employees to get to know the way of working and the capabilities of the others, the leaders must establish the team's objectives together with them and convey the expected results. As a result, employees will be less hesitant to express their opinions and ideas, and they will begin to think about achieving goals as a team and not as an individual. This stage can be recognized by the leader through the help, assistance and support that employees offer to others in carrying out work tasks. At this stage, positive feedback is important so that the team knows that its progress and achievements are recognized.

Within the company analyzed, 53.1% of employees believe that they always know the leaders' expectations regarding the tasks they have to perform, 34.4% quite often and 12.5% rarely. Company leaders appreciate in a percentage of 63.6% that they always convey their expectations, 27.3% quite often, and 9.1% rarely.

Hypothesis 3: The involvement of employees in decision-making and the improvement of processes within the company can ensure a more effective relationship between leaders and supporters by reaching the need to confirm their skills.

Fig. 5: How do you feel about your professional development within the company? (Supporters)

The company's employees consider their professional development within the company to be satisfactory and very advantageous, preferring to work in a team. Thus, most employees do not view their work as an individual effort, but rather as a group achievement. Thus they can assume a commitment to the team, leader or company, this increasing productivity and work dynamics. It is no longer necessary to involve the leader so strongly as an authority figure. You can increase the interaction with the staff, encourage them and maintain a proactive attitude, developing an environment of trust.

Fig. 6: Do you prefer to work independently rather individually? (Supporters)

The degree of satisfaction, involvement and motivation of the staff in the actions aimed at increasing the performance of relations with their leaders.

Hypothesis 1: Employee satisfaction is found in the level of involvement and motivation through effective actions of the company.

Fig. 7: Specify the performance evaluation methods and tools used within the company (Supporters – left, Leaders – right)

The most frequently used performance evaluation methods and tools within the company are: quarterly / annual evaluation of objectives, evaluation of the level of skill development, feedback sessions between manager and subordinate (min. once per quarter), and evaluation of results/list of responsibilities.

Fig. 8: Which of these are the most interesting and most used ways to motivate the team?

The ways in which employees are motivated are: adequate salaries, performance bonuses, recognition of the value of the employee, flexible schedule, safe working conditions, organization of team building/parties with the team, improvement programs.

The main purpose of motivating employees is their proven role in improving workplace performance. For this, company leaders need to know their employees and the climate within the teams, in order to apply the best strategies to retain talent in organizations and attract new competent candidates.

Hypothesis 2: The level of motivation of employees is found in the quality of relationships.

Fig. 9: If you achieve performance, do you enjoy recognition from your leader? (Supporters); If employees are performing, do you capitalize on the results? (Leaders)

In proportion of 71.9% (supporters) and 72.7% (leaders) the employees' performances are recognized by the leaders. The objective evaluation and appreciation of individual performance is the basis of on-the-job training and improvement of work motivation. Labor relations generate and maintain the climate favorable to the achievement of individual and team performances.

Fig. 10: Do you think that your leader listens to you and analyzes your ideas/proposals for improvement? (Supporters) – Do you pay attention, listen and analyze employees' ideas/suggestions for improvement? (Leaders)

More and more organizations discover the power of teams in carrying out tasks related to creativity, which contribute to innovative solutions for solving problems in an organization. In order for teams to play a greater role in the creativity process, an organization must create the necessary conditions for the manifestation of team creativity. It seems that within this company, employees' ideas and proposals

for improvement are listened to, approved, appreciated and implemented (if applicable). Employees are encouraged to find ways to improve processes and procedures.

Identifying the degree of satisfaction of the relationship within the company, both from the point of view of the employees and the leaders

Hypothesis: Within a successful company, the level of satisfaction of relations between leaders and supporters must be perceived equally by both parties involved, avoiding situations where the relationship is considered optimal only from the perspective of employees or leaders.

Fig. 11: Do you think that there is an effective communication and collaboration relationship between the leader and the team members?

Both the employees and the leaders, within this company, believe that there is an effective communication relationship between them. Internal communication is one of the means by which the smooth running of the organization is ensured, and a good business strategy also includes a constant dialogue with employees. They need to know what is happening in the company, what are the directions of activity and in what way their jobs will be influenced by the management's decisions. Developing good employee communication requires long-term work and a well-designed strategy, not just spur-of-the-moment initiatives. Thus, communication must be constant and consistent, be represented by the transmission of relevant messages, of interest and with impact on its receivers.

Fig. 12: Rate your overall satisfaction with the relationship between leaders and employees

From the diagrams above, it can be seen that both employees and leaders consider the employee-leader relationship to be satisfactory. Living and working together, we must know each other's interests. Mutual knowledge is the basis of our existence. Any professional group has a leader, any institution, regardless of its profile and mission, has a certain structure, created to ensure the functions or activities necessary to achieve the proposed goal. The entire activity of an organization is carried out by people, framed according to certain principles, specific work groups, who play certain professional roles, have

a certain status and a certain status. That's why the relationship between leaders and employees is very important, it makes the company run smoothly.

Discussion and conclusions

The dyadic relationship and communication between leader and employees is a key point in organizations. Ideally, this exchange should give the leader the opportunity to direct his employees to the proper completion of tasks, clarify the context of the reward, and provide social and emotional support.

The research of the central objectives (the level of relationship between leaders and supporters, the degree of satisfaction, involvement and motivation of the staff, the degree of satisfaction of the boss-employee relationship) and the hypotheses (the freedom to plan, program, organize and control one's own work, the involvement of employees in decision-making and process improvement, employee satisfaction, employee motivation level) provide the following set of conclusions:

- The trends are to transform existing businesses into agile businesses, able to deal with rapid changes, and workers to be guided to deal with any situation
- The degree of involvement, respectively, motivation of a company's staff can be found in the attitude and interest they have in relation to the company
- Organizational climate is determined by labor relations
- Work organization increases the quality of professional life
- The degree of employee motivation influences the company's results

Following the application of the questionnaire, we can appreciate that, at the level of the studied company, communication is efficient and satisfactory, from the perspective of correlating the level of expectations with that of the perceived reality, both for employees and for leaders. Communication is carried out in a relaxed, friendly manner, characterized by availability for collaboration, consultation, offering useful information and support in overcoming any professional difficulties.

The seniority of the employees and leaders, denotes the fact that within this company, the activity is carried out with employees and leaders who appreciate the values and professional relations within the company. Seniority on the job leads to more effective networking due to more in-depth knowledge of internal procedures, manufacturing processes and personnel.

Regarding the employees' freedom to plan, schedule, organize and control their own work, we can highlight that the company encourages employees to take responsibility for the activities they carry out. Through the freedom to organize and plan their own way of working, trust is given to employees, this being a very good supporter of the relationship between them and the leaders. By encouraging employees to control their own work, leaders can achieve higher performance by empowering employees. Employees know their tasks much better, so communication between them can be free of employees' fear of failing or giving wrong information.

Also, the results expected by the leaders are transmitted to the employees. In order for the employees to get to know the way of working and the capabilities of the others, the leaders must establish the team's objectives together with them and convey the expected results. As a result, employees will be less hesitant to express their opinions and ideas, and they will begin to think about achieving goals as a team and not as an individual.

The company's employees consider that their professional development within the company is satisfactory and very advantageous, preferring to work in a team. Thus, most employees do not view their work as an individual effort, but rather as a group achievement.

The main purpose of employee motivation within the company is its proven role in improving workplace performance. For this, company leaders need to know their employees and the climate within the teams, in order to apply the best strategies to retain talent in organizations and attract new competent candidates. Within this automotive company, employees' ideas and proposals for improvement are listened to, approved, appreciated and implemented (if applicable). Employees are encouraged to find ways to improve processes and procedures.

References

Brower, H. H., Schoorman, F. D., and Tan, H. H.

2000

"A Model of Relational Leadership: The Integration of Trust and Leader-Member Exchange." *Leadership Quarterly*. 11, (2), 227-250. Research Collection Lee Kong Chian School Of Business

Cătoiu I. et al.

2002

Cercetări de marketing (Marketing Research), Uranus Publishing, Bucharest

Ferris, G. R., Liden R.C., et al.

2009

"Relationships at Work: Toward a Multidimensional Conceptualization of Dyadic Work Relationships." *Journal of Management* 35(6) 1379–1403.

Cojocaru, V., Bretan, F. I.

2018

"Tipologia stilurilor de conducere și influența lor asupra eficienței organizației" *Studia Universitatis Moldaviae*, 2 (112): 125-131

Miricescu D.,

2015

Relația susținător – lider și influența acesteia asupra funcționării eficiente a echipelor (Follower – Leader Relation And Its Influence On Teams' Efficiency), *Review of Management and Economic Engineering*, vol. 14 / nr.1(55), Todesco Publishing House, Cluj-Napoca, 65 – 77

Țuțurea, M., Miricescu, D., Moraru, G.M., and Grecu, V.

2010

"Leadership în organizații." Editura Universității "Lucian Blaga" din Sibiu. Sibiu

Văcar, A., Miricescu, D.

2013

"Leadership – a Key Factor to a Successful Organization – Part II, Elsevier, ScienceDirect – *Procedia Economics and Finance* 6 (2013), 430 – 435

Zohar, I.

2016

"Imaginea leadershipului și a liderului în epoca globalizării." Phd Thesis, "Babeș-Bolyai" University Cluj-Napoca. European Studies Faculty